

Title: Towards a testing framework to characterize chloride resistance of concrete based on cement paste-scale tests

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Abstract: Replacing clinker with supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) is one of the successful strategies available for a widespread reduction of the clinker factor, thus reducing the carbon footprint in cement. Although several studies in the past focused on the mechanical performance of clinker substitution, there are questions regarding the rapid assessment of long-term durability performance of a given cement composition. Most of the durability testing standards prescribe tests at the concrete scale, while durability of concrete is strongly dependent on the binder composition. Hence, this study aims to propose a testing framework to characterize concrete-scale chloride resistance from cement paste-scale tests, thereby reducing the number of variables to be tested and allowing for quicker adoption of novel low-carbon blends. Accelerated steady-state migration and bulk resistivity tests were conducted at both paste and concrete scales on a diverse set of binders, including SCMs such as fly ash, slag, natural pozzolan, limestone, calcined clay, and recycled concrete fines. In addition, chloride ion penetrability at concrete scale was also characterized using Rapid Chloride Permeability Test (RCPT). The limits of applicability of the correlations among steady-state diffusion coefficient, bulk resistivity, and RCPT charge passed were identified for all the systems. Also, threshold values to characterize chloride ingress resistance of concrete were proposed based on bulk resistivity and mini-migration diffusion coefficient of pastes. Overall, this study aims to develop a testing framework, where the chloride resistance of cement paste and concrete scales are linked together, thereby facilitating the development of low-carbon durable cement blends.